

THE ROLE OF INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN LEARNING A FOREIGN LANGUAGES

¹Abdurashidova Madina Sharifjon qizi, ²Feruzza Boymurodova

¹Uzbekistan State World Languages University Faculty of philology foreign languages, Student

²MA International Education Teacher, Uzbekistan State World Languages University

Telephone: ¹+998945903311, ²+998946732355

Email: 1abdurashidova17m@gmail.com, 2boymurodovaferuzza555@gmail.com

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Abstract. *In today's interconnected world, the importance of multilingual communication for personal, academic, and professional success cannot be overstated. Innovative technologies have revolutionized the landscape of language learning, offering a plethora of interactive and engaging tools that cater to diverse learning styles and preferences. The convenience and accessibility of mobile apps, online platforms, and virtual reality tools have democratized language education, allowing learners to engage with lessons and activities at their own pace and convenience. Moreover, these technologies enable personalized learning experiences that are tailored to individual needs and skill levels. By providing interactive content and feedback mechanisms, technology encourages active participation and continuous progress tracking. Collaboration among students, teachers, and language experts worldwide further enriches the learning experience by facilitating meaningful cultural exchanges. Ultimately, the integration of innovative technologies in language education not only enhances language skills and cultural awareness but also equips learners with the global communication abilities necessary for success in an increasingly multilingual world. As technology continues to advance, its pivotal role in shaping the future of education is undeniable, ensuring that students are well-prepared for the linguistic challenges of tomorrow.*

Keywords: *Innovative technologies, online platforms, mobile apps, multimedia technology, creative activities, computer-based learning*

Аннотация. *В сегодняшнем взаимосвязанном мире нельзя недооценивать важность многоязычного общения для личного, академического и профессионального успеха. Инновационные технологии революционизировали область изучения языков, предлагая множество интерактивных и увлекательных инструментов, отвечающих различным стилям обучения и предпочтениям. Удобство и доступность мобильных приложений, онлайн платформ и виртуальных инструментов демократизировали языковое образование, позволяя учащимся участвовать в уроках и занятиях на своем собственном темпе и удобное время. Более того, эти технологии обеспечивают персонализированные образовательные опыты, адаптированные к индивидуальным потребностям и уровням навыков. Предоставляя интерактивный контент и механизмы обратной связи, технология поощряет активное участие и непрерывное отслеживание прогресса. Сотрудничество между студентами, учителями и языковыми экспертами со всего мира дополнительно обогащает образовательный опыт, облегчая значимые культурные обмены. В конечном итоге интеграция инновационных технологий в языковое образование не только улучшает языковые навыки и культурное осознание, но также оснащает учащихся глобальными коммуникативными способностями, необходимыми для успешности во все более многоязычном мире. Поскольку технологии продолжают*

развиваться, их ключевая роль в формировании будущего образования неоспорима, обеспечивая подготовку студентов к языковым вызовам завтрашнего дня.

Ключевые слова: *Инновационные технологии, онлайн платформы, мобильные приложения, мультимедийные технологии, креативные занятия, компьютерное обучение*

Anotatsiya. *Innovatsion texnologiyalar bugungi aloqador dunyoda shaxsiy, ilmiy va kasbiy muvaffaqiyat uchun ko'p tilli kommunikatsiyaning ahamiyatini ta'kidlaydi. Texnologiyalar yangiliklari til o'rganish sohasini rivojlantirgan, turli o'quv usullariga moslasha oladigan interaktiv va qiziqarli vositalar taklif etadi. Mobil ilovalar, onlayn platformalar va virtual texnologiyalarining qulayligi va qo'llanishliligi til o'qitishni demokratlashtiradi, o'rganuvchilarga darslar va mashg'ulotlarga o'zlarining xohishiga va qulayliklariga mos ravishda qatnashish imkoniyatini beradi. Bundan tashqari, bu texnologiyalar shaxsiy talablarga va ko'nikma darajalarga moslangan shaxsiy o'rganish tajribasini taqdim etadi. Interaktiv materiallar va aloqa mexanizmlarini taqdim etilishi orqali texnologiya faol qatnashishni va doimiy rivojlanishni rag'batlantiradi. O'quvchilar, o'qituvchilar va dunyo bo'ylab til mutaxassislarining hamkorlik qilishi orqali ma'naviy va madaniy aloqalarni almashinishi yordamida ta'lim tajribasini boyitadi. Umumiy holda, til o'qitishda innovatsion texnologiyalarni integratsiya qilish, faqat til ko'nikmalarini va madaniyatni, ma'rifatni rivojlantirishga yordam bermaydi, balki yaxshi bir ko'nikmaga ega bo'lshga yordam beradi.*

Kalit so'zlar: *Innovatsion texnologiyalar, onlayn platformalar, mobil ilovalar, multimedia texnologiyasi, kreativ mashg'ulotlar, kompyuter asosida o'quv*

One of the main advantages of innovative technologies in language learning is their convenience and ease of use. Mobile apps, online platforms and virtual reality tools allow learners to access language lessons, hands-on activities and interactive content anytime, anywhere. This flexibility allows students to engage in language learning activities at their own pace and convenience, eliminating barriers to entry and accommodating different learning styles and preferences. Innovative technologies enable the creation of personalized learning experiences tailored to the individual needs, preferences and skill levels of students. Technology offers interactive and engaging content that encourages students to actively participate in language learning activities. Technology supports continuous learning and progress tracking through features like progress dashboards, analytics, assessments, and feedback mechanisms. It fosters collaboration among students, teachers, and language experts globally, enabling meaningful language and cultural exchanges. Innovative technologies enhance language education by providing interactive, personalized learning experiences. Effective technology use improves language skills, cultural awareness, and global communication abilities. As technology advances, its role in language learning will continue to grow, shaping the future of education and preparing students for a multilingual world.

Modern technology plays a crucial role in language education by aiding in various language learning aspects like reading, writing, listening, and speaking. For instance, to comprehend spoken language effectively, tools like computers, media players, and CDs become essential. Listening is a key component in language acquisition, demanding learners to focus on pronunciation, grammar, vocabulary, and meanings simultaneously.

Innovative technologies revolutionized the teaching and learning of foreign languages. Here are some important points that highlight their impact:

1. Online Language Learning Platforms: Platforms like **Duolingo**, **Rosetta Stone**, and **Youghlish** have made language learning more accessible, interactive, and personalized. These platforms offer a variety of exercises, games, quizzes and interactive lessons to effectively engage students.

Duolingo is a popular language-learning platform that offers courses in multiple languages through interactive exercises, games, and quizzes.

- Usage: Users can choose from a wide range of languages and work through lessons that cover vocabulary, grammar, listening, speaking, and reading skills.

- Recommendations: Practice regularly to build consistency in language learning.

- Engage with the speaking exercises to improve pronunciation and fluency. Take advantage of the spaced repetition feature to reinforce learning.

Youghlish is a website that provides pronunciation examples using real-life videos sourced from various media platforms like YouTube.

- Usage: Users can search for a word or phrase in their target language and listen to native speakers pronounce it in context.

- Recommendations: Use **Youghlish** to practice pronunciation and intonation by listening to how native speakers pronounce words or phrases. Repeat after the native speakers to improve your own pronunciation.

Rosetta Stone is a language-learning software that offers interactive courses for users to learn languages through immersive methods, such as visuals, audio, and text.

- Usage: Users interact with the software by engaging in lessons that focus on vocabulary, grammar, pronunciation, and conversation practice. The software uses speech recognition technology to evaluate users' pronunciation.

- Recommendations: Regular practice is key to making progress in language learning. Consistent daily practice sessions are more effective than occasional longer sessions. Utilize all the features offered, such as speaking exercises, listening comprehension activities, and vocabulary drills. Supplement Rosetta Stone with other resources like practice conversations with native speakers, reading books in the target language, or watching movies/shows in that language for a well-rounded learning experience. **Rosetta Stone** is suitable for beginner to intermediate language learners looking to build a solid foundation in a new language. Students, professionals, travelers, and language enthusiasts can benefit from using **Rosetta Stone** to improve their language skills. Users who prefer self-paced and interactive learning methods will find **Rosetta Stone's** platform engaging and effective. By following these recommendations and incorporating **Rosetta Stone** into your language-learning routine, you can effectively enhance your language skills and proficiency. Enjoy your language-learning journey with **Rosetta Stone!**

2. Mobile Apps: Mobile apps have revolutionized language learning by providing students with easy access to lessons, vocabulary exercises, pronunciation help, and real-time feedback. Apps like **HelloTalk** and **IELTS assistant app**, make language exchange with native speakers easier, improving speaking and listening skills

The IELTS Assistant app is designed to help individuals prepare for the International English Language Testing System (IELTS) exam, which assesses the English language proficiency of non-native English speakers.

- Usage: The app provides practice tests, study resources, tips, and strategies to improve English language skills in the four key areas: Listening, Reading, Writing, and Speaking.

- Recommendations: Use the app regularly to familiarize yourself with the exam format and practice under timed conditions. Utilize the feedback provided after each practice test to identify areas for improvement. Make use of the speaking exercises to enhance fluency and pronunciation..

3. Virtual Reality (VR) and Augmented Reality (AR): VR and AR technologies create immersive language learning experiences by placing students in realistic environments where they can practice speaking, listening, and interacting with virtual characters or scenarios. It improves language retention and fluency.

VR Language: In VR applications, language plays a crucial role in creating immersive experiences for users. This includes dialogue between characters, text-based instructions or prompts, and voice commands. VR developers often focus on designing realistic and engaging dialogue to enhance the storytelling and user interaction within the virtual environment.

AR Language: Language in AR applications is used to provide contextual information, instructions, and labels for virtual objects overlaid on the real world. This can include text annotations, subtitles, or audio cues that help users understand and interact with the augmented elements seamlessly. AR developers need to consider the placement and presentation of language elements to ensure they are easily accessible and enhance the user experience.

4 .Online Tutoring and Video Conferencing: Platforms like Zoom, Skype and Google Meet have made it easy for students to connect with language tutors and teachers around the world. Virtual classes allow for real-time interaction, personal feedback, and one-on-one training.

5. Regarding Artificial Intelligence Chatbots: Language chatbots, like AI-driven conversational partners, support students in honing their conversational abilities. These chatbots facilitate dialogues, address queries, and offer feedback on language proficiency.

Innovative educational technologies play a pivotal role in enhancing the quality and efficacy of education. They foster collaboration among teachers, students, and groups, promoting a shared vision and unity of purpose. These technologies have immense potential in creating conducive conditions and environments for learners to realize their inherent abilities and blossom as individuals.

In conclusion, the key benefits of computer-based learning in teaching English include the ability to create interactive exercises, use sound cards for speech comparison with native speakers, and utilize graphics for visual representation of activities and vocabulary. Beyond just communication, learners must acquire skills in utilizing new technologies to enhance their learning autonomy. This includes being able to handle situations when language resources are insufficient, possessing effective study habits, evaluating their own speech and advancement, and resolving learning obstacles.

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